

MOLECULAR STUDY OF *TOXOPLASMA GONDII* INFECTION IN GOATS AT BASRAH PROVINCE.

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Abstract

Toxoplasma gondii is the causative agent of toxoplasmosis, one of the most common parasitic infections of humans and pets. In this study, the parasite was isolated from chopped diaphragm muscles from naturally infected goats in Basrah Province. 45 meat samples were collected from local goats during the period from October 2020 to March 2021. The samples were examined microscopically and (36) positive samples containing the parasite were recorded with percentage infection (80%). The current study included a genetic detection of *T. gondii* in the above animals to find out the infection rate and spread of the parasite in local goats meat. Polymerase chain reaction technique using specific primers was used for genetic detection of the parasite in goats. The PCR-positive samples recorded an infection rate of (34.8%). The sequence of the nitrogenous bases of the DNA of the parasite were studied together with the reading of the genetic tree of these samples. The reading of phylogenetic tree matched with the main branch tree that carries the sequence MZ717192.

Keywords: *Toxoplasma gondii*, Molecular study, Goats, Basrah

Introduction

Toxoplasmosis in humans may occur vertically by tachyzoites that are passed to the fetus via the placenta, or horizontally, which may involve three life-cycle stages: (1) ingesting sporulated oocysts from cats, (2) ingesting tissue cysts in raw or under cooked meat, or (3) ingesting tachyzoites in blood products or primary offal (viscera) of many different animals, organ transplants, and unpasteurized milk (Tenter *et al.*, 2000)(1). Livestock animals, when infected during pregnancy, suffer from parasitemia, which can infect the placenta and fetus and ultimately result in fetal resorption, miscarriage, death, or mummification. Often the young ones are born, but die shortly after birth (Engeland *et al.*, 1996)(2).

Materials and methods

Meat sample collection

Meat samples were collected after slaughtering from the goats in butcher shops in Basrah province. Meat samples were collected in clean plastic sterile containers, kept in cool container,

and transported immediately to the laboratory. Each sample was treated separately, and after removing adipose tissues from them they were cut in to small pieces (7-26) gm in weight.

Isolation of parasite from meat

Meat samples were minced thoroughly in sterilized mincer containers (20ml). Mixed with equal volume of normal saline, the solution was filtered by using gauze to avoid large particles. Then placed in clean test tube centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes, the supernatant discarded and the sediment was then resuspended by normal saline, these process were repeated 3 times. Pencillines 1000 I.U and 100 mg of streptomycin were added into the solution to prevent contamination. Two to three drops of PBS were added to the precipitate. Many clean dry smear slides were prepared from the sediments of the above samples.

A drop of the same sediment was placed on a clean glass slide for preparing smear, left to dry and after fixation by methyl alcohol 90% for ten minutes, stained for 30 minutes with 10% Giemsa stain for further details and examined and photographed under light Leica microscope supplied with digital camera drawing scale.

Molecular study (PCR) :

Primer 529

Primer 529 for *Toxoplasma gondii* were provided by Macrogen company south Korea.

Forward (F1):

5'-CGC TGC AGG GAG GAA GAC GAA AGT TG-3

Reverse (R1):

5'-CGC TGC AGA CAC AGT GCA TCT GGA TT-3

PCR Thermocycler

Round of amplification was carried out as follows :

No	Steps	Time	Temperature	Cycle
1	Initial Denaturation	7 min	94°C	1 cycle
2	Denaturation	1 min.	94°C	35 cycle
	Annealing	1min	55°C	
	Extension	1min	72°C	
3	Final Extension	10 min	72°C	1 cycle

DNA Extraction

DNA was extracted by using Geneid kit U.S.A and done according to company manual instruction as follows :

1. Dry clean smear were scraped from the slide and added to 200µl lysis buffer in 1.5 ml micro centrifuge tube.

2. 20 μ l of Proteinase K added, then mix by pipetting and incubated at 60°C for 5 minutes.
3. 200 μ l of GSB Buffer added then mixed by shaking vigorously, incubated at 60°C for 5 minutes then inverted the tube every 2 minutes.
4. During incubation, required volume of Elution Buffer (200 μ l/sample) was transferred to a 1.5 ml micro centrifuge tube and heated to 60C.
5. 200 μ l of absolute ethanol were added to the sample lysate and mixed immediately by shaking vigorously for 10 seconds. If precipitate appeared, it broke up as much as possible with a pipette.
6. A GS Column placed in a 2 ml Collection tube, all of the mixture (including any insoluble precipitate) transferred to the GS Column, centrifuged at 14-16,000 x g for 1 minute. Following centrifugation, if the mixture did not flow through the GS Column membrane, the centrifuge time increased until it passed completely. The 2 ml Collection tube discarded which containing the flow-through then the GS Column transferred to a new 2 ml Collection tube. It is important to noticed that the lysate and ethanol are mixed thoroughly to yielded a homogeneous solution.
7. 400 μ l of W1 Buffer were added to the GS Column, centrifuged at 14-16,000 x g for 30 seconds then discarded the flow-through. The GS Column placed back in the 2 ml Collection tube. 600 μ l of Wash Buffer (it important to make sure that absolute ethanol was added) added to the GS Column, centrifuged at 14-16,000 x g for 30 seconds then discarded the flow-through. The GS Column placed back in the 2 ml Collection tube, centrifuged again for 3 minutes at 14-16,000 x g to dry the column matrix.
8. The dried GS Column transferred to a clean 1.5 ml micro centrifuge tube. 100 μ l of pre-heated Elution Buffer, TE Buffer or water added into the center of the column matrix. Let stand for at least 3 minutes to allow Elution Buffer, TE Buffer or water to be completely absorbed. Centrifuge at 14-16,000 x g for 30 seconds to elute purified DNA.

Gel Electrophoresis

PCR products were analyzed by loading in 1.5% Agarose as following steps:

1. 1.5% Agarose gel was prepared in using 1X TBE and dissolving in water bath at 100°C for 15 minutes , after that, left to cool 50°C.
2. Then 2 μ l of ethidium bromide stain were added into agarose gel solution.
3. Agarose gel solution was poured in tray after fixed the comb in proper position, after that, left to solidified for 15 minutes at room temperature, then the comb was removed gently from the tray and 5 μ l of PCR product were added into each comb well and 5 μ l of (100pb Ladder) in one well.
4. The gel tray was fixed in electrophoresis chamber and fill by 1X TBE buffer. Then electric current was performed at 100 volt and 80 AM for 50 minutes.
5. PCR products were visualized by using ultraviolet transiluminator and the bands were photographed.

DNA Sequencing :

To identify the genetic variation (Genotype) between *T. gondii* isolate as well as standard NCBI isolates 25 µl volume of PCR product and 17 pica mole for each of the first and second Nested primers were send to Macrogen company, South Korea. The analysis of DNA sequence were done according to genetic analysis V.X. (Mega X) and multiple sequence alignment. Phylogenetic tree was drown according to VPGMA programme.

Statistical analysis :

Chi- square were used to analyzed data obtained in the present study with probability $P \leq 0.05$.

Result

The percentage of positive cases of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in goats meat.

Out of 45 goats meat examined, 36 samples were positive with 80%. There was no significant difference in percentage infection between positive cases of *Toxoplasma gondii* in goats according to the months of years (p .value= 0.147). The higher percentage is (100%) and the lower percentage is (67%) table(1).

Table (1): The percentage of positive cases of *T. gondii* in goats according to months of years.

Month	Goats		
	Examined No.	Positive No.	Percentage %
October 2020	15	10	67%
November	4	3	75%
December	5	4	80%
January 2021	6	6	100%
February	5	4	80%
March	10	9	90%
$X^2 = 8.171$, DF = 5 , p. value= 0.147			

The samples photographed under light Leica microscope as shown in Figures (1).

Figure (1) : *Toxoplasma gondii* in goats muscle smear.

Electrophoresis and PCR of *T. gondii* from goats meat on agarose gel 1.5%.

DNA was extracted from goats diaphragmatic muscle samples using geneid Kit. PCR was processed using B1 gene primer. Amplification of B1 gene fragment (529bp) was identified in all samples on agarose gel 1.5% (Fig 2).

Fig (2): Electrophoresis of PCR product of *T. gondii* (dry smear) from goats meat on agarose gel 1.5%.

L : Ladder (100 – 2000bp)

Lane 1- 4 : Goats meat positive samples (529bp)

Partial sequence of 529 pb *T. gondii* isolate.

The sequence of the local goats *T. gondii* isolate showed 100% identity. It was deposited at NCBI with asseccion number MZ717192. The sequence of the local goats *T. gondii* isolate was shown on Table 2.

Table (2): Partial sequence of 529 bp *T. gondii* goats isolate.

1	TAGCGACCTAAGAAAACAGACATCAATAAAGTCTC CGAAGGCCGAAGATTCGGATGAGTGGGTGTCGCAC TTGGCTACCCACTATAGTGGGATCTCCCCACGACG TTACCGTGCCTGGGGAGTTTTCTCTACGGGGGTA AAAGATACACCGGTATGCGATCCAGACGAGCCAC GCTTTCCTCGTGGTGATGGCGCAGAGAATTGACGA GTGGAGAAGAGGGCGAGGGAGACAGAGTCGGAG GCTTGGACGAAAGGAGGAGGGGTTGATGAGT AA	278	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	A 529 primer set 4 samples
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Phylogenetic tree of *T. gondii* from goats.

The phylogenetic tree which demonstrate the genetic relationship of *Toxoplasma gondii* isolates from muscles of goats. MEGAX genetic analysis was used, Maximum Likelihood , Bootstrap test (1000 replicates) and Bootstrap (%) to show the values on the branches of the evolutionary tree shown in Fig (3) and table 3.

Figure (3) : A phylogenetic tree of *T. gondii* from goats and global reference sequences.
Sequence identity of local goats *T. gondii* isolate and NCBI- Blast homology

Sequence between current local goat *T. gondii* isolate and NCBI- Blast homology from different countries was showed in table 3.

Table (3): Sequence between current local goats *T. gondii* isolate and NCBI- Blast homology from different countries.

No	Accession No.	Country	Host	Organ and strain
1	DQ779191.1	China	-	Strain RH
2	FJ656209.1	USA	-	Strain RH
3	AF146527.1	Netherlands	-	Strain RH
4	DQ779196.1	China	-	-
5	KX963354.1	Iraq	Sheep	Brain
6	MH884748.1	Iran	Sheep	Brain
7	MH884736.1	Iran	Sheep	Brain
8	MG003442.1	Israel	common bottlenose dolphin	brain, liver, spleen, lung
9	KX781159.1	China	Cat	Feces
10	MH884735.1	Iran	Sheep	Brain

Sequence alignments of B1 gene (529) bp.

The sequence nucleotide alignments of B1 gene (529) bp of *T. gondii* genotypes from goats muscle isolates and percentage of DNA identity was shown in Fig (4) and Table (4).

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cagCgatCTttGAggAgAGAtATCAGgActGTAgatGaAGGCGAgGgTgaGGATGaGgGG
T.gondii_This study : T...GAC..AA..AA.C...C...AT.AA..CTCC.....A.A.TC.....T... : 60
T.gondii_RH_China : .....C..... : 60
T.gondii_RH_USA : ..... : 60
T.gondii_RH_Netherlands : ..... : 60
T.gondii_China : .....G.....A.....T.A... : 60
T.gondii_Iraq : .....G.....A.....T.A... : 60
T.gondii_Iran : .....CA..... : 60

GTGgCGTggTTGGgaAgCgaCgAgAGTcGGAgagggagAaGATGTTtCCGtGctTGGctg
T.gondii_This study : ...T..CAC...CT.C.C.C..T.T...G...TCTCCCC.C..C...A.....C...GGA : 120
T.gondii_RH_China : ..... : 119
T.gondii_RH_USA : ..... : 119
T.gondii_RH_Netherlands : ..... : 119
T.gondii_China : .....G..... : 119
T.gondii_Iraq : .....G..... : 119
T.gondii_Iran : .....A.....TC..... : 119

ctTTTCCTggAgGgTgGaAAAaGAgACACCGGaATGCGATCTAGACGAGaCgACGCTTTC
T.gondii_This study : G.....CT.C..G..T.....T.....T.....C.....C.C..... : 180
T.gondii_RH_China : .G..... : 178
T.gondii_RH_USA : ..... : 179
T.gondii_RH_Netherlands : .....C..... : 179
T.gondii_China : ..... : 178
T.gondii_Iraq : ..... : 178
T.gondii_Iran : .....A..... : 178

CTCGTGGTgATGGCGgAGAGAATTGAaGAGTGGAGAAGAGGGCGAGGGAGACAGAGTCCG
T.gondii_This study : .....C.....C..... : 240
T.gondii_RH_China : ..... : 238
T.gondii_RH_USA : ..... : 239
T.gondii_RH_Netherlands : ..... : 239
T.gondii_China : ..... : 238
T.gondii_Iraq : ..... : 238
T.gondii_Iran : ..... : 238

AGGctTGGACGAaGGAGGAGGcGTaGgagAGgAA
T.gondii_This study : .....A.....G..T..AT...T... : 278
T.gondii_RH_China : ..... : 276
T.gondii_RH_USA : ..... : 277
T.gondii_RH_Netherlands : .....G..... : 277
T.gondii_China : ..... : 276
T.gondii_Iraq : ..... : 276
T.gondii_Iran : .....TC.....A..A... : 276
    
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Table XX. DNA Identity matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1: <i>T.gondii_This study</i>	100	72.5	74.3	74.3	74.6	75.1	75.8
2: <i>T.gondii_Iran</i>		100	94.6	94.6	95.7	96.4	95.7
3: <i>T.gondii_China</i>			100	100	97.5	98.3	97.5
4: <i>T.gondii_Iraq</i>				100	97.5	98.3	97.5
5: <i>T.gondii_RH_China</i>					100	99.3	98.6
6: <i>T.gondii_RH_USA</i>						100	99.3
7: <i>T.gondii_RH_Netherlands</i>							100

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T.gondii_This study : cagcagctttgaggagagatatcaggactgtagatgaaggcagggtgatgaggatgagggg : 60
T.gondii_RH_Netherlands : cagcagctttgaggagagatatcaggactgtagatgaaggcagggtgatgaggatgagggg : 60

T.gondii_This study : gtggcgtggttgggaagcgaagcagagagtcggagagggagaaagatgtttccgtgcttggctg : 120
T.gondii_RH_Netherlands : gtggcgtggttgggaagcgaagcagagagtcggagagggagaaagatgtttccgtgcttggctg : 119

T.gondii_This study : cttttcctggagggtggaaaagagacacggatgcgatctagacgagacgacgcttttc : 180
T.gondii_RH_Netherlands : cttttcctggagggtggaaaagagacacggatgcgatctagacgagacgacgcttttc : 179

T.gondii_This study : ctctggtgatggcggagagaaattgaagagtggagaagagggcgagggagacagagtccg : 240
T.gondii_RH_Netherlands : ctctggtgatggcggagagaaattgaagagtggagaagagggcgagggagacagagtccg : 239

T.gondii_This study : aggcttggacgaaggagaggaggcgtaggagaggaa : 278
T.gondii_RH_Netherlands : aggcttggacgaaggagaggaggcgtaggagaggaa : 277
    
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Nucleotide sequence alignment with RH_ strain from Netherlands.

The relationships between the present sequence haplotypes study and 5 RH_ strains from Netherlands was shown in Fig (5).

Figure (5) : Nucleotide sequence alignments of the present study and 5 RH_ strains from Netherlands.

Discussion

Depending on the microscopic examination of meat, the current study showed the highest infection rate (80%) in goats. These results indicated that goats are more susceptible to infection, and this is consistent with what Oncel and Vural (2006)(3) mentioned. The increase in the rate of infection in goats in this survey may be due to the nature of grazing and feeding on pastures contaminated with *T. gondii* parasite oocyst and on the places of littering and damaged food that cats shelter in, in addition to that goats are more susceptible to toxoplasmosis than other ruminants (Dubey, 1980; Dubey and Beattie, 1988)(4),(5). Pasture, feed and drinking water contaminated with oocysts are potential sources of postnatal infection in animals (Heidari *et al.*, 2013)(6). In recent years, increased attention has been paid to *T. gondii* infection because toxoplasmosis is the common causes of miscarriage in young ruminants, with its economic losses compared to other animals such as cattle (Acici *et al.*, 2008)(7). Inability to perform serological examination of animals prior to slaughter may increase infection rates and make it difficult to diagnose toxoplasmosis clinically. The slaughter of many infected and aborted goats may increase the risk of toxoplasmosis. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has indicated that toxoplasmosis is one of the most important parasitic diseases of zoonotic origin due to its high incidence in human

which indicated the need to investigate its occurrence, both in humans and animals (Andreoletti *et al.*, 2007)(8).

The highest percentage of *T. gondii* in goats (100%) was found in January and the lowest percentage (67%) in October. This may be related to the availability of favorable conditions for the maturation of the oocyst to become contagious Morin *et al.* (2012)(9), (Yan *et al.*, 2016)(10).

In the current study the total infection rate of *T. gondii* in goat muscle samples examined by PCR technique was (34.8%), (15/43). This result was less than what was mentioned by Al-taie and Abdullah (2008)(11) where they found that the infection rate was (41.67%) (5/12) tested by the PCR technique in Sulaymaniyah. In Wasit, a high infection rate in goat muscles was recorded (42.8%) using RT-PCR technique (Khiri, 2016)(12).

The high infection rate of goats in the current study was conferred by the results of several international studies. Goats are a source of food, especially milk, which is more widely used for children than cattle's milk (Prelezov *et al.*, 2008)(13). In general, infection rates differ between sheep and goats. The reason was the difference in the way of infection, where the goats eat the upper part of young trees and grasses rather than the lower part of the plant where the infective stage of the parasite is located (Sharif *et al.*, 2007)(14).

The method of isolation of parasite DNA by PCR technique is a relatively simple method, sensitive, reproducible and low cost Su *et al.* (2010)(15) compared to the biological model with mice that lasts 3 to 6 weeks or cell culture that takes 4 to 10 days to show results (Liu *et al.*, 2015)(16). The sensitivity of this method depends on the technique of DNA extraction, sample processing and the nature of the parameters (primers) used in the amplification reaction (Switaj *et al.*, 2005)(17). Nested PCR technique can be used, which has high sensitive and less costly (Burg *et al.*, 1989)(19).

The meat samples analyzed in the current study were taken from adult animals and therefore were more susceptible to *T. gondii* parasite, as studies showed that age is a risk factor for toxoplasmosis in sheep (Hamilton *et al.*, 2014; Amdouni *et al.*, 2017)(20),(21).

Conclusion

It was concluded from the current study that eating undercooked goats meat is one of the important sources of toxoplasmosis infection in Basrah. The reading of phylogenetic tree matched with the main branch tree that carries the sequence MZ717192.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank the College of Education for Pure science, Basrah University, for providing facilities.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that no conflict of interest exists.

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DOI: [10.1016/j.meatsci.2017.07.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2017.07.004)

Article Highlight:

1- Given the importance of toxoplasmosis, as a zoonotic disease and its close relationship to community health, the study was conducted to isolate and identify the local strain of *T. gondii* from the diaphragm muscles of naturally infected goats in Basrah Province using PCR (conventional methods).

2- The DNA sequencing of the B1 gene of *T. gondii* and the phylogenetic tree were studied in this study to determine the genetic relationship between local isolation and global spread.